

Ethics Requirements: PROTECTION OF PERSONAL DATA

Deliverable 11.2

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Lead Partner: ITENE

Contributor(s): All partners

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

In the EU over 100 million tonnes of biowaste are thrown away each year. Currently, 75% of this goes to landfill or is incinerated, causing major environmental problems biowaste produces greenhouse gases when it decomposes and contaminates soil and groundwater. Landfilling of biowaste goes against the principle of a circular economy and is a waste of nutrients, energy and resources for bioproducts. In this sense, SCALIBUR project aims to demonstrate innovative solutions to transform urban biowaste into high value-added products, helping cities to increase their recycling rate and creating new circular economy business opportunities.

This project engages citizens and stakeholders from the three pilot territories (Madrid, Albano and Kozani) along the biowaste value chain, starting at the household level to improve citizen understanding about the importance of waste separation and to increase the acceptance of products made from biowaste. In this sense, there is a clear need to make an ethical evaluation from the conceptual stage of the proposal not only to respect the legal framework but also to enhance the quality of the research. Ethical research conduct implies the application of fundamental ethical principles and legislation to scientific research in all possible domains of research, the quality of the management and potential impact. The ethics work package ensures that all research activities carried out under SCALIBUR are conducted in compliance with fundamental ethical principles.

This deliverable provides detailed information about the procedures implemented for data collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction complying with national and EU legislation as well as information on the consent procedures. Further information about Protection of Personal Data can be found in D1.2 (Data Management Plan).

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